

**THE PROCEDURE FOR MAINTAINING FOREIGN CURRENCY
ACCOUNT NUMBERS OF INDIVIDUALS AND LEGAL ENTITIES BY
COMMERCIAL BANKS**

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***Abstract.** This article presents scientific and theoretical views on the importance of remote banking services in banking activities, the channels of their provision and the possibility of further expanding it.*

***Keywords:** remote banking services, internet banking, Banking-Client, online banking,*

“Mobile banking” (WAP-banking), “SMS banking”, “Uzcard”.

INTRODUCTION

Today, one of the main tasks facing the development of the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to improve the quality of banking services, expand the scope of services and bring them to the level of banks of developed countries.

In the words of our president, in this regard, special attention should be paid to the development of modern banking services and the popularization of banking services. In the "Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" adopted by the decree of the President of Uzbekistan on February 7, 2017, it is also "reform of the banking system, deepening the capitalization and stability of the deposit base of banks, and their the task of strengthening financial stability and reliability, further expanding crediting of promising investment projects and small business and entrepreneurial entities.

In fact, the development of the market of services of commercial banks

creates not only the distribution of capital to the national economy, but also the provision of information to the population, acceleration of payments, and a number of other conveniences and opportunities. Based on this, studying the experience of foreign countries in the field of banking services and implementing the positive aspects of this experience based on the internal situation in the banking system of Uzbekistan is one of the urgent issues of today.

Taking into account the above, in recent years, a number of other documents were adopted, which envisage the liberalization of the banking system and adaptation to the conditions of free competition.

In particular, on March 23, 2018, the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on additional measures to increase the popularity of banking services No. 3620 should be adopted, existing problems in the provision of banking services and implemented by banks determined the measures. Including:

- Innovative products for making cashless payments, that is including the development and promotion of non-contact and mobile technologies;
- Introduction of non-contact and mobile technologies, first of all, in the spheres of social and household services, transport, trade, catering, especially in the regions;
- Ensuring mutual cooperation with international payment systems, etc.

MAIN PART

Modern information technologies, the introduction of new banking products and services create conditions for the expansion of the market of banking services in our country. As the relations of the market economy develop in our republic, commercial banks are diversifying their activities by increasing the types of retail operations and services provided to customers.

In recent years, banks have been offering various innovative banking

services in order to improve the quality of services provided to customers. Currently, all commercial banks are opening their websites on the Internet and regularly enriching them with information about the bank's activities, new types of services and conditions, and information related to the interests of customers. Through the website of the Central Bank, interactive state services have been launched. The expansion of the use of mobile phones among the population led to the establishment of "Mobile-banking" (WAPbanking) and "SMS-banking" services by banks. Work on continuous improvement of remote bank account management systems (Bank-Client, Internet-banking, Mobile-banking, SMS-banking, etc.) on a national scale should be systematically carried out by all banks, on the one hand, the development of the national banking system on the other hand, it creates conditions for further strengthening of market mechanisms in the republic's economy.

Also, the traditional "Bank-client" system, which provides remote banking services, is widespread in our republic and is implemented in all banks. To use this system, a special program is installed on the client's computer, and interaction with the bank's information system is ensured through communication channels. However, the possibility of using this system is limited due to the need to connect to a specific workplace and use specialized programs when using the "Bank-client" system. Therefore, the online banking (internetbanking) system, which provides operation through the Internet network and a simple browser, that is, a widespread program that provides the client access to the network, is widely used.

Internet banking technology creates additional convenience for both the bank and customers. In particular, the client has the opportunity to carry out banking transactions on his account, without going to the bank, through the Internet from any place, at any time, and the state of the account, the receipt of funds, the reflection of payments can receive information about actions such as delivery. This creates the advantages of saving time and money for the client,

freely choosing a bank regardless of the distance and proximity of the address, and quickly managing their funds.

Also, in cooperation with commercial banks that are participants of the "Uzcard" interbank payment system, the creation of a national technological platform that works in the "on-line" mode will allow the client to manage his card accounts in real time through Internet banking services, utility and other provides an opportunity to make payments.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As of January 1, 2019, the number of users of remote bank account management systems increased by almost 1.0 times compared to the beginning of 2018, and reached 3.4 million. Of these, the number of individuals using bank account remote management systems for bank plastic cards and bank deposit accounts is more than 7.6 million, and the number of legal entities and individual entrepreneurs using remote bank account management systems is 360,000. did

According to the information of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, at the end of 2018, the total volume of deposits attracted by commercial banks increased by 25.2 percent compared to 2017 and amounted to 44.6 trillion. amounted to soum. Also, due to the expansion of the quality and scope of banking services provided with the extensive use of modern information and communication technologies, the volume of banking services increased 1.2 times in 2018, their share in the total financial services reached 88%, and the number of users is growing dynamically. .

In particular, the number of users of "Internet-banking" and "Bank-client" software complex services increased by 135,600, while the number of users of "Mobile-banking" and "SMS banking" services was 1,906,500.

In our country, all banks are constantly taking measures to develop remote banking services. As a result of these measures, as of January 1, 2020, the total number of users of the service is 10 million. increased from

The data shows that today the weight of banking services provided to retail customers in the banking system is increasing year by year. Nevertheless, the scope of banking services provided to individuals through "Internet-banking" with bank credit cards, securities, which are widely used in Western countries, is developing slowly.

In order to achieve the strategic goal of improving the market of retail banking services in Uzbekistan, banking activities should be developed according to the following directions:

- standardization and automation of the process of delivery of banking services.
- development of a strategy for the introduction of modern sales, including the development and optimization of the branch system.
- expanding the scope of banking services and improving their quality.

We believe that the fulfillment of these tasks will make it possible to further improve the market of banking services and meet the demands of bank customers. In conclusion, as a result of the analyzes conducted on the prospects for the development of remote banking services in Uzbekistan, the following proposals and recommendations were developed:

1. Each commercial bank should develop its own strategic program for the development of remote banking services in commercial banks, the development of the remote customer service system. In this program, it will be necessary to develop a road map for the step-by-step transfer of all types of services to remote and online mode.

In this road map, it is necessary to mention the source of funding, the implementation period, the department responsible for implementation, and the project launch period.

2. Currently, the types of services provided remotely by commercial banks include utility and other payments, card-to-card money transfers, online conversion, online deposit services, as well as retail lending services in some

banks. It is advisable to increase their species at the next stage. In particular, these include sending and receiving funds abroad through integration into international money transfers, including the service of virtual emission of plastic cards.

3. It is natural that the development of remote banking services creates the need to identify customers. Taking this into account, it would be appropriate to create opportunities for integration from the database of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in the event of the need to identify the employee in the service of the client to all mobile banking services.

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